

A new species of the *Jujubinus curinii* species complex: *J. roseus* n. sp. (Gastropoda, Trochidae: Cantharidinae) from the Alborán Sea

Una nueva especie del complejo de especies *Jujubinus curinii*: *J. roseus* n. sp. (Gastropoda, Trochidae: Cantharidinae) del Mar de Alborán

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ABSTRACT

Jujubinus roseus n. sp. is described from the Alborán Sea. It belongs to the *J. curinii* species complex, the so-called “smooth *Jujubinus*”, and is compared with the other members of the complex: i.e. *J. curinii* Bogi & Campani, 2005, *J. eleonora*e Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, *J. trilloi* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, *J. alboranensis* Smriglio, Mariottini & Oliverio, 2015 and *J. browningleeae* Smriglio, Mariottini & Swinnen, 2018. All species of this complex have very restricted known ranges.

RESUMEN

Jujubinus roseus n. sp. se describe desde el mar de Alborán. Pertenece al complejo de especies *J. curinii*, el llamado “*Jujubinus* liso”, y se compara con los demás miembros del complejo: i.e. *J. curinii* Bogi & Campani, 2005, *J. eleonora*e Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, *J. trilloi* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, *J. alboranensis* Smriglio, Mariottini & Oliverio, 2015 y *J. browningleeae* Smriglio, Mariottini & Swinnen, 2018. Todas las especies de este complejo tienen áreas de distribución conocidas muy restringidas.

KEY WORDS: Mediterranean Sea, Recent, Trochidae, *Jujubinus*, new species.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mar Mediterráneo, Reciente, Trochidae, *Jujubinus*, nueva especie.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Jujubinus* Monterosato, 1884 includes a relatively small group of trochoidean gastropods (Vetigas-

tropoda, Trochidae, Cantharidinae) prevalently living in shallow waters, occasionally found down to 80 m, and

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normally associated to algae and/or marine angiosperms (MARIOTTINI *ET AL.*, 2013; SMRIGLIO *ET AL.*, 2015 and references therein) although recent works have suggested deeper waters for some species (ARDOVINI, 2006; ROLÁN & SWINNEN, 2013; SMRIGLIO *ET AL.*, 2016). *Jujubinus* has been used to include many cantharidine species worldwide distributed and with a typical trochiform shells but there is growing evidence (WILLIAMS *ET AL.*, 2010; URIBE *ET AL.*, 2017; our data, unpublished), that this genus should be restricted to the East Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea.

A typical feature of most *Jujubinus* species, is the presence of numerous tiny prosocline lamellae in the interspaces of 4–8 spiral cordlets. However, BOGI & CAMPANI (2005) described the first species of *Jujubinus* lacking lamellae in the interspaces of its flat spiral cordlets: *Jujubinus curinii* Bogi & Campani, 2005, from the coralligenous bottoms of the Strait of Messina. Later on, a few other similar species sharing this peculiar shell sculpture have been described from the Mediterranean Sea and the neighbouring Atlantic Ocean (SMRIGLIO *ET AL.*, 2014, 2015, 2018), all with very restricted geographic ranges and all allopatric: *J. eleonorae* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014 from the Skerki Bank, Sicily Channel; *J. trilloi* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, from the Talbot Bank, Sicily Channel; *J. alboranensis* Smriglio, Mariottini & Oliverio, 2015 from the Alborán Sea; *J. browningleeae* Smriglio, Mariottini & Swinnen, 2018 from the Gorringe Bank, Atlantic Ocean.

Here we describe a further new taxon, *J. roseus* n. sp., based on material from the Alborán Sea, collected sympatrically with *J. alboranensis*.

Abbreviations and acronyms
 CS-PM, Carlo Smriglio-Paolo Mariottini collection, Rome, Italy;
 FS, Frank Swinnen collection, Lommel, Belgium;
 H, Height;

W, Width;
 lv, live collected specimen (s)
 sh, empty shell (s)
 LIME, Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy;
 MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales;
 MNHN, Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France;
 MCZR, Museo Civico di Zoologia of Rome, Italy;
 MO, Marco Oliverio collection, Rome, Italy;
 RBINS, Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Brussels, Belgium;
 SEM, Scanning Electron Microscopy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sediment samples were collected during the Campaña Fauna Iberica IV (1996) carried out by MNCN, sampling by SCUBA diving the infralittoral zone on the ridge surrounding Alborán Island, Spain. The vouchers of the new species consisted of 6 lv and 5 sh. Additionally, we have used for comparison:

J. curinii, 200 sh, Scilla, Strait of Messina, 42 m depth, CS-PM;

J. eleonorae, 122 sh, Skerki Bank, Sicily Channel, 37 m depth, CS-PM;

J. trilloi, 90 sh, Talbot Bank, Sicily Channel, 25 m depth, CS-PM;

J. alboranensis, 101 sh, Alborán Island, 30-37 m depth, MO; 20 sh, Alborán Island, 30-37 m depth, CS-PM; 29 lv, Alborán Island, 10-34 m (Campaña Fauna Iberica IV stn 311B1);

J. browningleeae, holotype and one paratype, Gorringe Seamount, 130 miles off Cape St. Vincent, RBINS: I.G.33787/MT.3687 and FS, respectively.

Current systematics is based on WoRMS. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) photographs were taken at the Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy (LIME, Università "Roma Tre", Rome, Italy), using a Philips XL30.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795
Family TROCHIDAE Rafinesque, 1815
Genus *Jujubinus* Monterosato, 1884

Type species: *Trochus matoni* Payraudeau, 1826 (by subsequent designation of von Martens, 1885: 52, in the Zoological Record), accepted as *Jujubinus vulgaris* (Risso, 1826).

Jujubinus roseus n. sp. (Figs. 1-11)

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Type material. *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 lv; off Alborán Island, infralittoral bottom; 35° 58.00'N, 02° 58.46'W; 37 m; Jul. 1996; Fauna Ibérica IV leg., sta. 315B; MNCN 15.05/35835H. *Paratypes*: SPAIN • 5 lv and 5 sh including seven juveniles; same data as for holotype; MNCN 15.05/35835P.

Etymology: from the Latin adjective *roseus*, referring to the background pink colour.

Locus typicus: Alborán Island, Spain (35.9666°N, -2.9743°W), infralittoral bottom, at a depth of 37 m, Alborán Sea.

Diagnosis: Medium size and slightly turriculate shell; sculpture of incised and flat spiral cords; prosocline lamellae absent between cords.

Description (in parenthesis data of the holotype): Shell of medium size for the genus, height 5.5–8.9 (8.2) mm, width 4.3–6.3 (6.1) mm, conical, light.

Protoconch of 0.85 whorls, 0.27 mm in width, sculptured by two spiral threads.

Teleoconch of 4.5–6.5 (6.5) slightly convex whorls with angled shoulder.

Sculpture of 6–10 (11) flat, closely set abapical spiral cordlets of about the same strength, broader than interspaces, 2–3 (2) peripheral ones not very distinguishable, forming the basal cord, slightly shouldered and ratchet. Suture incised.

Base convex, with 13–14 (13) regularly spaced, basal broad and flat spiral cordlets of variable size; umbilicus

closed also in juveniles, covered with a whitish-pinkish callus.

Aperture quadrangular, with columellar callus thickened in central and basal portion. Interior of the aperture whitish-pinkish nacreous.

Colour of protoconch and initial teleoconch whorls bright intense pink; remaining whorls and base pale pink, with brownish-reddish flexuous axial lines of different size and arrangement.

Soft parts: Epipodial tentacles light purple-reddish. Foot reddish, sole creamy yellowish. Cephalic tentacles purple-reddish, with a dorsal purple stripe. Eye stalks reddish, eyes black encircled by creamy-yellow. Snout reddish with a creamy terminal band. Cephalic lappets whitish.

Distribution: Currently known only from the type locality.

DISCUSSION

Jujubinus roseus n. sp. (Figs. 1-11) shares with the five known species of the *J. curinii*-complex (SMRIGLIO ET AL., 2014, 2015, 2018), the teleoconch sculpture of flat spiral cords, without the prosocline lamellae in the interspaces (SEM Fig. 4), which are instead typically present in the type species of the genus

and in most of the Atlantic and Mediterranean species. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. is known only from the type locality, in the Alborán Sea, where it has been collected sympatric with (but rarer than) *J. alboranensis*: this is the first case of sympatry between two species of the *J. curinii* complex (Fig. 12). *J. alboranensis*, which

Figures 1-3. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. 1: holotype, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8.2 mm (H) × 6.1 mm (W); 2: paratype, 5.5 mm (H) × 4.3 mm (W); 3: paratype, MNCN 15.05/35835P, 4.8 mm (H) × 4.2 mm (W). Alborán Island, Spain, 37 m depth.

Figuras 1-3. Jujubinus roseus n. sp. 1: *holotipo*, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8,2 mm (*alto*) × 6,1 mm (*ancho*); 2: *paratipo*, 5,5 mm (*alto*) × 4,3 mm (*ancho*); 3: *paratipo*, MNCN 15.05/35835P, 4,8 mm (*alto*) × 4,2 mm (*ancho*). *Isla de Alborán, España, 37 m de profundidad.*

may also show a stepped shoulder in large specimens, is distinguished by the fewer spiral cords (6 in *J. alboranensis* v. 13–14 in *J. roseus* n. sp.) and by the consistently different colour (bright red in the protoconch and initial whorls of

teleoconch, alternating brownish-reddish and yellowish-orange spiral stripes in the remaining whorls and base, with the upper part of the brownish-reddish stripes dotted with red in *J. alboranensis* v. bright intense pink proto-

Figure 4. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. A, B: holotype, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8.2 mm (H) × 6.1 mm (W), SEM pictures of the teleoconch; C-G: SEM details of teleoconch and protoconch sculpture. Arrows show the two spiral cords on the first whorl of protoconch.

Figura 4. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. A, B: holotipo, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8,2 mm (H) × 6,1 mm (W), imágenes de microscopio electrónico de barrido de la teleoconcha; C-G: detalles MEB de la escultura de la teleoconcha y protoconcha. Las flechas muestran los dos cordones espirales en la primera vuelta de la protoconcha.

conch and initial teleoconch whorls, pale pink the remaining whorls and base, with brownish-reddish flexuous axial lines in *J. roseus* n. sp.).

Jujubinus curinii also show a somehow stepped shoulder in adult shells, but it differs from *J. roseus* n. sp. in the smaller maximum size (5.7 mm of

Figure 5. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. A, B: paratype, 8.9 mm (H) x 6.3 mm (W), Alborán Island, Spain, 37 m, CS-PM; C: living specimen from Alborán Island, Spain, photographed in aquarium (photo by Diego Moreno, reproduced from PEÑAS ET AL. 2006: fig. 424).

Figura 5. *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. A, B: paratipo, 8,9 mm (H) x 6,3 mm (W), Isla de Alborán, España, 37 m, CS-PM; C: ejemplar vivo de la Isla de Alborán, España, fotografiado en acuario (foto de Diego Moreno, reproducida de PEÑAS ET AL. 2006: fig. 424).

J. curinii v. 8.9 mm for *J. roseus* n. sp.), in the fewer spiral cords (7–8 in *J. curinii* v. 12–13 in *J. roseus*) and a constantly different colour pattern (shiny reddish-

brown background, with red apex and edge of the base with white spots in *J. curinii* v. bright intense pink protoconch and initial teleoconch whorls, pale pink

Figures 6-11. Comparison of species in the *Jujubinus curinii* complex. 6: *Jujubinus curinii* Bogi & Campani, 2005, 5.3 mm (H) × 4.1 mm (W), Scilla, 42 m depth, Strait of Messina, Mediterranean Sea, CS-PM; 7: *Jujubinus trilloi* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, holotype, MNHN 25882, 5.4 mm (H) × 4.6 mm (W), Talbot Bank (37°30'00"N, 11°40'00"E), infralittoral bottom, 25 m depth, Sicily Channel, Mediterranean Sea; 8: *Jujubinus eleonora*e Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, holotype, 5.7 mm (H) × 4.7 mm (W), MNHN 25883, Skerki Bank (37°45'00"N, 10°50'00"E), infralittoral bottom, 37 m depth, Sicily Channel, Mediterranean Sea; 9: *Jujubinus alboranensis* Smriglio, Mariottini & Oliverio, 2015, holotype, 6.8 mm (H) × 5.3 mm (W), MNHN IM-2000-30131, Alborán Island, Spain, 30-37 m depth, bioclastic sand; 10: *Jujubinus browningleeae* Smriglio, Mariottini & Swinnen, 2018, holotype, RBINS: I.G.33787/MT.3687, 5.2 mm (H) × 3.8 mm (W), Gorringe seamount, 130 miles off Cape St. Vincent, Portugal North-Eastern Atlantic Ocean; 11: *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp., holotype, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8.2 mm (H) × 6.1 mm (W), Alborán Island, Spain, 37 m.

Figuras 6-11. Comparación de especies del complejo *Jujubinus curinii*. 6: *Jujubinus curinii* Bogi & Campani, 2005, 5,3 mm (H) × 4,1 mm (W), Scilla, 42 m de profundidad, Estrecho de Messina, Mar Mediterráneo, CS-PM; 7: *Jujubinus trilloi* Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, holotipo, MNHN 25882, 5,4 mm (alto) × 4,6 mm (ancho), Banco Talbot (37°30'00"N, 11°40'00"E), fondo infralitoral, 25 m de profundidad, Canal de Sicilia, Mar Mediterráneo; 8: *Jujubinus eleonora*e Smriglio, Di Giulio & Mariottini, 2014, holotipo, 5,7 mm (H) × 4,7 mm (W), MNHN 25883, Banco Skerki (37°45'00"N, 10°50'00"E), fondo infralitoral, 37 m de profundidad, Canal de Sicilia, Mar Mediterráneo; 9: *Jujubinus alboranensis* Smriglio, Mariottini & Oliverio, 2015, holotipo, 6,8 mm (alto) × 5,3 mm (ancho), MNHN IM-2000-30131, Isla de Alborán, España, 30-37 m de profundidad, arena bioclástica; 10: *Jujubinus browningleeae* Smriglio, Mariottini & Swinnen, 2018, holotipo, RBINS: I.G.33787/MT.3687, 5,2 mm (alto) × 3,8 mm (ancho), Monte submarino Gorringe, a 130 millas del Cabo San Vicente, Portugal, Océano Atlántico nororiental; 11: *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp., holotipo, MNCN 15.05/35835H, 8,2 mm (H) × 6,1 mm (W), Isla de Alborán, España, 37 m.

Figure 12. Distribution of *Jujubinus browningleeae*, *Jujubinus curinii*, *Jujubinus eleonora*, *Jujubinus trilloi* (green circles), and *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. and *Jujubinus alboranensis* (red circle).

Figura 12. Distribución de *Jujubinus browningleeae*, *Jujubinus curinii*, *Jujubinus eleonora*, *Jujubinus trilloi* (círculos verdes) y *Jujubinus roseus* n. sp. y *Jujubinus alboranensis* (círculo rojo).

the remaining whorls and base, with brownish-reddish flexuous axial lines in *J. roseus* n. sp.).

J. trilloi differs in its shell of smaller size (rarely up to 6.5 mm *v.* 8 mm in *J. roseus* n. sp.), the fewer, flat spiral cordlets (6–8 *v.* 12–13 in *J. roseus* n. sp.); it has a different colouration, bright red protoconch, remaining whorls and base brown-reddish, with evident axial opisthocline brown-reddish axial lines.

J. eleonora differs more neatly in its shell of smaller size (rarely up to 6 mm *v.* 8 mm in *J. roseus* n. sp.), the conical and slightly convex outline, without a stepped shoulder; it has also a different sculpture of broad and high spiral cords, and a different colouration, with a greenish-reddish background and yellowish-orange interspaces.

Finally, *J. browningleeae*, the only species of the complex currently known from the Atlantic Ocean, differs from *J. roseus* n. sp., in the fewer spiral cordlets (7–8 in *J. browningleeae* *v.* 12–13 in *J.*

roseus n. sp.). In addition, the two type specimens differ in their colouration: the holotype with apical whorl reddish and the remaining whorls and base with dark-brown background and wavy and narrow axial yellow stripes, and the paratype with protoconch and teleoconch whorls with bright reddish background and yellow wavy lines more evident on the peripheral cord and the base.

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